

An In-Depth Analysis of Cohesion Utilization in the English Language: Implications for Effective Communication and Textual Coherence

Haneen Saad Kadhim

*Department of English language, College of Education,
Sawa University, Almutbana, Iraq*

Abstract

This study focuses on the link between coherence and the English language notion of cohesiveness. Cohesion is defined as the way in which different elements of a text or speech are linked together to create a unified and integrated whole. The study identifies the challenges in determining the appropriate level of cohesion for a given text and how factors such as audience, purpose, and context can affect cohesion. The aims of the research are to provide learners with a better understanding of cohesion in English and to demonstrate the importance of cohesion in producing clear and effective communication. The paper is divided into three sections: the first section introduces the problem, aims, scope, procedure, and hypothesis; the second section provides a detailed explanation of the definition, general meaning, models, and types of cohesion; and the third section examines lexical and grammatical cohesion in more detail. The theory argues that English language learners typically don't understand the ideas of cohesion and coherence, which leads to poor writing that is illogical and grammatically incorrect. The research methodology involves data collection from English books, analysis, comparison of essays on cohesion, and consultation with instructors of English. Ultimately, this research highlights the importance of cohesion in achieving coherence and producing effective communication in English. The practical study of grammatical cohesion conducted in the English Department of Sawa University's College of Education aimed to assess students' comprehension of linguistic phenomena such as conjunction, ellipsis, references, and substitution. The study involved 54 participants, comprising of 36 females and 18 males, who were presented with 18 different prompts and asked to identify the linguistic phenomenon present in each response. The study's analysis revealed that participants identified these linguistic phenomena differently for each prompt, with some responses predominantly identified as conjunction, while others were predominantly identified as ellipsis or references. These findings provide insight into how individuals interpret and use language and can contribute to the development of linguistic theories and models.

Keywords: *Cohesion, conjunction, ellipsis, Grammatical Cohesion, Lexical Cohesion, substitution.*

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Introduction

Edmondson (1981) defined conversation as any reactionary communication that involves sharing and at least two participants in a non-formalized environment, without reference to any particular rules or convention that may be considered effective. "Those surface structure features of utterance or text which link different parts of sentences or larger units of discourse" is what Crystal (2003) defines as cohesiveness. In a similar vein, Beaugrande and Dressler (1981) define coherence as the way that the elements of the surface text—that is, the words that we actually hear or see—are related to one another within a flow. Verschueren (1999) defined coherence as the explicit labeling of relationships within a discourse or text. According to many definitions, cohesion and coherence are synonymous.

According to Thompson (1994), cohesion is a multifaceted phenomena wherein the meaning relations underlying the text are concurrently signed openly by the lexico-grammatical cohesion and the intonation choices, which indicate the clause relations. According to Blum-Kulka (1986), cohesion is an explicit link that exists between textual elements that are denoted by language-specific markers. Text and cohesiveness are synonymous. The substance that holds a text's meaning relations together and transforms it into a cohesive whole is called cohesiveness. It may be viewed as a collection of syntactic and semantic elements that directly connect the sentences in a text. Cohesion, as a component of the language system, is essential to comprehending and interpreting written material.

Two categories-grammatical (reference, substitution, ellipses, and conjunction) and lexical (reiteration and conjunction)-help cohesiveness accomplish this goal. (1976, Halliday and Hasan). Coherence, on the other hand, denotes the text's balance and clarity of meaning. Cohesion is the manner by which two phrases are connected together. (Sulaiman, Ali, 2022). When it comes to connecting thoughts and concepts to one another, cohesion is useful. Long-term experience teaching English suggests that students' comprehension of consistency and cohesiveness in the language will soon be less than minimal. (Sulaiman, Ali, 2022). It is important to remember that coherence is under the purview of syntax. Conversely, coherence plays a meaningful function in language. To put it another way, coherence is a semantic problem. Hence, coherent texts make it simple for readers to grasp what is being communicated by flowing coherently. To put it another way, it's a condition or circumstance when all the components or notions come together to create a cohesive whole. (Al-Sulaiman, 2022).

The Problem of the Study

The challenges of the study are:

1. Figuring out how cohesive a particular text or speech should be. A manuscript that lacks coherence may be hard to read and comprehend, whereas one with excessive cohesiveness may come across as repetitious or boring. Achieving the ideal balance is crucial to good communication.
2. Being aware of the ways that context, audience, and goal influence cohesiveness. The degree of cohesiveness needed for various audiences and goals may also alter, and

the meaning of cohesive devices can change based on the situation in which they are employed.

In general, studying coherence in English entails learning how various textual or spoken components interact to produce a meaningful and cogent message.

Aims

The purpose of the study is to provide learners with some basic concepts regarding English cohesiveness. The function of cohesiveness is demonstrated by pointing out the logical order in which ideas occur inside sentences.

Scope of the Study

The research is divided into three sections. The first portion comprises an introduction, a list of difficulties, objectives, study scope, methodology, and hypothesis. The definition of cohesiveness, its general meaning, models of cohesiveness, varieties of cohesiveness, lexical and grammatical cohesiveness, and a more thorough description of the many forms of cohesiveness are all included in section two. Section three will next provide a real-world research that involved 54 Sawa University students, data gathering procedures, data analysis, and more.

Procedure

The following are the techniques that this study pursues:

1. English-language literature on the topic are the source of the data. These are arranged based on the requirements of the paper.
2. The data are occasionally evaluated in terms of cohesiveness with reference to coherence.
3. A comparison of a few cohesion-related writings helps to define the word and improve comprehension of it.
4. English instructors across various scientific levels are invited to offer their perspectives on the paper's subject.

Hypothesis

It is proposed that:

- a. English language learners typically don't understand the meanings of cohesion and coherence.
- b. When producing texts, they are incapable of creating logical sentence connections.
- c. When learners are ignorant of these ideas, their writing suffers; in that their work is consistently illogical and grammatically incorrect.

The Definition of Cohesion

Cohesion is crucial to understanding both English and other languages, even though each language has unique patterns that are used to communicate the links between people and events. As a result, under no circumstances could these patterns be altered or broken in the event of translation, which must be understood by its readers. According to Halliday and Hassan (1976:5–6), cohesiveness is represented by grammar, or "grammatical cohesion," which has the kinds "reference, substitution,

ellipsis, conjunction." It is also expressed through vocabulary, or "lexical cohesion," which has the types "repetition and collocation."

According to Halliday and Hasan (1976: 4), coherence is defined as the semantic relationships that exist within the text. When certain discourse elements' interpretations depend on one another, cohesion is produced. Thus, poor sentence structure has a detrimental effect on a text's semantics. According to Singh, coherence is what sets a coherent sentence pattern apart from a disjointed string of phrases in a speech. Singh (1979) as quoted by Kalil (2008)

It is described as the formal language manifestation of the pragmatic and semantic links between phrases and sentences in a text by Quirk et al. (1985: 1423). Richard (1985: 45) defines it also as the grammatical or lexical link among the various textual components. On the other side. Gee (1999: 159) draws the conclusion that authors and speakers must do more than only join clauses inside sentences in light of these viewpoints. According to Yule (2006: 126), a text's cohesiveness is determined by its internal links and relationships. It is concluded that incorrect sentence structures produce a random, semantically unintelligible content.

The General Meaning of Cohesion

The links between meaning in the text are displayed via a semantic unit known as cohesiveness. Cohesion results from the fact that the interpretations of certain components depend on the interpretations of other parts. It's also set up to function in case one part needs another, and the latter can only be completed by utilizing the former (Halliday and Hassan, 1976:4). In the words of Halliday and Hassan (1976:5–6), grammar, or "grammatical cohesion," is what cohesiveness is expressed by. It includes the types "reference, substitution, ellipsis, conjunction." Furthermore, it is conveyed through language, or "lexical cohesion," which includes "repetition and collocation." According to Schaeffer (2004:132), cohesive articles create connections between the structures of a sentence and other sentences. According to As-Subeihi (2008:82), cohesiveness may be achieved by the following techniques: lexical means, conjunctions, ellipses, repetition, and substitution. "Lexical linking and grammatical one" is the term for these methods (Shebl, 2009:105).

According to Al-Batashi (2013:57), cohesiveness is the method by which the linguistic process's component of continuity—that is, the sounds, words, and sentences—is produced in text form.

Models of Cohesion

Although Jakobson (1960) discussed the importance of patterning and repetition in the development of literary parallelism, Halliday and Hasan's landmark work *Cohesion in English* (1976) conducted the first significant examination into cohesion (As referenced in Martin, 2009; Malmkjar: 2010).

Language studies scholars and linguists have proposed a variety of methods for studying coherent devices. The paradigm that Halliday and Hasan offered in *Cohesion in English* (1976) is one example of this kind. Their comprehensive model has proven useful in a variety of research projects, including ESL (English as a Second Language), native oral discourse and composition, reading comprehension, academic discourse from non-native speakers, literary analysis (and consequently, religious books), genre constraints on cohesive ties selectivity, and reading comprehension.

This can be attributed to the taxonomy's comprehensiveness and clarity, which let researchers utilize the components most suited for their specific research objectives.

According to Halliday and Hasan (1976), there are five basic categories that may be utilized to address cohesion: reference, substitution, ellipsis, conjunction, and lexical coherence.

The linguistic form serves as the primary basis for classifying the "cohesive items," and the categories ought to be seen in the context of the lexico-grammatical system. Furthermore, the notion of connecting one section of a text to another within the same text serves as the foundation for the cohesiveness function. Overall, it gives the writing coherence and fluidity. Cohesion allows language users to provide all the details needed to explain the visual by giving them this. In other words, cohesion includes the grammatical formatting of phrases, clauses, and sentences that bring connectivity to the text (Halliday & Hasan 1976, p. 19).

Types of Cohesion

It is mainly achieved through the availability of two types of cohesive categories grammatical and lexical. Grammatical cohesion is created by reference, substitution, ellipsis, and conjunction. Lexical cohesion is brought by reiteration and collocation.

Lexical Cohesion

Language research is emphasizing the role that texts have in everyday communication. It is sometimes impossible to fully capture the useful function that language plays in communication in a single line. Thus, whether written or spoken, a text is the unit of communication, as was previously stated. Lexical coherence, in any event, is an essential component of cohesiveness in a text and is crucial to its development. Lexical coherence in a text is the result of two words having a semantic link of some kind. Put another way, they have semantic connections. Lexical cohesion is the reader's perception of the text's coherence as a result of the author's use of terms that have similar meanings.

The elements of a passage must be connected to create a logical unity of structure. Lexical cohesiveness is the term for this, and it solves the problem. On the other hand, lexical coherence also considers the meaning of the text. Furthermore, it addresses the relationships that exist between cohesive devices and lexical phrases to provide the strongest possible coherence. This type of coherence is typically achieved by lexical chains that enter a text and have distinct relationships with one another.

Grammatical Cohesion

The connections made between a passage's elements to create a cogent structural coherence is known as grammatical cohesion. Cohesion is indicated by Halliday and Hasan (1976: 27) because it is intimately associated with information structure. Functional textualism primarily teaches authors and linguists how to construct intelligible writings by connecting sentences. The connectedness of texts with situations is further enhanced by functional textual analysis. Linguists believe that conjunction, substitution, reference, and ellipsis are unambiguous signs of grammatical cohesiveness. The overall cohesiveness of texts is assessed using these cohesive techniques.

Conjunction

Using conjunctions is one of the most obvious strategies to achieve grammatical cohesiveness. Words that are utilized in the linking process are called conjunctions. One can join a series of clauses, phrases, or paragraphs using these words. (Larson, 389–844) In their study, Halliday and Hasan categorize conjunctions into four types.

1. Adjective conjunctions like moreover, or, and.
2. 2. Adversative Conjunctions: such as only, but, still;
- 3-Causal Conjunctions: such as, then;
4. Temporal conjunctions, such as first and last.

Habeeb (2006:46) gives three instances, however they are restricted to the first three categories of conjunctions.

1. She could have changed her mind or missed her train.
2. I would really like to take part, but I'm not very good at the game.
3. As the group got closer to the peak, the weather cleared.

They had seen nothing up to that point. Conjunctions are utilized to add to, clarify, and sometimes even serve as illustrations of what has been spoken. These words are used to contrast contemporary and historical data in order to draw attention to differences or offer an alternative point of view.

These techniques can help establish links between newly discovered data and previously discussed cause and effect as well as temporal relationships.

Substitution

Another method for joining phrases inside a text is replacement, which happens when proforms substitute words or other textual elements. As opposed to ellipsis, which removes a word or phrase from a sentence, replacement occurs. Therefore, proforms are thought of as compensating for terms or elements that have previously been discussed.e.g :

1. Which cake slice do you prefer? 'The large one is what I'd prefer. Rather than saying "piece of cake," one is used. Pronouns that take the place of nouns, such as the following, might also be said:
2. Since the clothing was filthy, I placed it in the washing machine. The pronoun "shirt" takes the place of the noun "shirt." Substitution is implied by other cases.
3. John is already aware. Everyone is in agreement. The word knows is substituted with does in the second clause.
4. That grocery store is where everyone shops. Even the underprivileged do. Buys from the first clause are replaced with do in the second phrase. It should be mentioned that substituting words prevents repetition and gives the conversation more linguistic heft. These proforms are usually utilized to make reference to earlier data or items that have been referenced previously. This method of joining phrases undoubtedly aids in drawing attention to the novel material in texts.

Ellipsis

is one of the most often used strategies for paragraph coherence in writing. It helps writers create coherent works with logical links. Ellipsis is the elimination of a part of a sentence when it is assumed that the previous debate has clarified its meaning. Due to its ability to eliminate repetition without impairing the general meaning of the phrase, it is the most often used technique for doing so. The complete meaning is preserved by the context. Even when a word or phrase is removed, the meaning remains intact. Frequently used in discussion as an example is:

- 1.What are you doing? studying. The full form of the answer would be I am studying.

The pronoun and the auxiliary are deleted to avoid repetition. The crucial reason behind making ellipses is to draw attention to new information by escaping to repeat the previously-mentioned information, e.g.

2. I have not spoken to that blonde girl, but I will in the future. in the above sentence the ellipted part of the sentence is equal to the given information that is found in the first clause. Williams (1989: 47) claims that ellipsis is actually a particular type of substitution, but there is no synonym or similar term for lexical items. Like a

3. He refers to it as a zero replacement. Mary tidied the space. Linda is in the kitchen. Since it is clear from the overt verb in the clause before, the verb in the second clause is removed. There are two sorts of ellipses that linguists agree upon: example ellipses that are dependable on linguistic context are listed below:

4. If you say so, I mean it. (serious)

5. Mary is tidying up the room while Linda refuses to. (Make the space neat) The phrases "tidy the room" and "serious" are included in parenthesis to indicate the removal of any language background. The remaining ellipses, for example, don't depend on context.

6. Serves you right since it is right for you.

Please forgive me. I ask your forgiveness.

7. I'm sorry I was unable to attend. I apologize for being unable to attend.

9. happy to see you - You are welcome to visit.

9. Are you looking for someone? Are you trying to find someone?

Textual Referential Device Types of Reference.

1. The term "backward reference" describes the usage of a word or phrase in place of one that has already been mentioned. The most often used coherent device in text composition is this one. - The technical word for this kind is anaphora. There are three instances of anaphoric reference in written texts. They are: a. Making use of a pronoun in place of the noun indicated before.

b. Modifying a noun that has already been mentioned with the indefinite article by using the definite article.

c. Swapping a term that has previously been mentioned for a synonym or hyponym. Three instances that relate to each of the three circumstances individually are as follows:

2. My sister is on the phone with someone. She argues that he needs the pamphlet she handed him.

3. As I sat at the window, I noticed a guy and a lady conversing at the door of the home. The woman had a purse, while the male wore a short coat.

4. The restaurant had a ton of delicious food, but I should continue eating light because I was meant to be slimming. Further instances include the pronoun "they" in place of two boys and the pronoun "he" in place of a cab driver.

5. Forward Reference: Another well-liked cohesive element, this one is also technically known as cataphora. Notice that there will be a cataphoric reference example shortly.

6. Maybe I shouldn't tell you this, but she used to wear a full-length skirt when she was younger. Certain sentences may have metaphorical connections to the phrases that

follow. However, these applications are quite uncommon and typically not required to create a text, for example

7. You might find this entertaining. The town has been invaded by a new bird vendor.

8. That was never supposed to happen. Five men left the battle against the enemy.

Lines (7) and (8)'s starting clauses provide the listener hints that make them think they're hearing something different. Cataphoric connections are used in the previous sentences to prepare listeners or readers for the information that will come next. Textual reference is produced by two consistent referential devices, anaphora and cataphora. It is a grammatical allusion to anything that occurs either before or after in the sentence. It's crucial to keep in mind that situational reference is the opposite of textual reference and usually relates to things outside of language.

In addition to the previously listed references, there is one more that lacks coherence. Exophora is a term used exclusively to characterize abstract concepts without providing their exact meaning. This reference differs from the previously stated powerful references that provide coherence when connecting disparate parts. Since the term's prefix *exo* means "outside," the writer will not identify people or events that are described in this way because they are not part of the text. Since it doesn't combine two ideas into a text, this reference isn't considered a coherent device.

Practical study of Grammatical Cohesion

A research was conducted to evaluate students' understanding of grammatical cohesiveness in the English department at Sawa University's College of Education. There were thirty-six female participants and eighteen male participants in the research.

In order to determine if a response is a conjunction, ellipsis, reference, or substitution, the research asked 18 questions. For every question, the number of participants—male and female—who recognized each sort of response was noted.

Data Collection Methodology

The data was collected by through forms filled by the students including the below categories:

Table 1. Questionnaire

Category	Question
General	Age
	Gender
Questions	1. I grabbed the ball and kicked it to the person who was playing takraw ball after the person who kicked it unintentionally struck my feel.
	2. I once departed for school at 7:00 a.m. on a Monday.
	3. left wearing nice clothing, a cap or tie, but that day I wore a span skirt (a narrow skirt) instead of my usual loose skirt because it was dirty.
	4. I was ceremonial at the moment.
	5. I did rather well on it.
	6. I didn't pass out until the ceremony was finished this time.
	7. We were informed right away following that ceremony
	8. To go into the classroom and start our first instruction. Specifically, Indonesian.
	9. After the first subject was completed, we moved on to mathematics for the second subject. Math has previously been passed as a subject.
	10. It's 09.30 when we should have started the break.

	11. Ever since, we have made use of our downtime by filling our stomachs with food.
	12. I once crossed the field on my way to the canteen.
	13. Numerous students play volleyball and takraw ball on the field.
	14. I neglected to take off the flimsy skirt I was wearing.
	15. I kicked him without waiting for permission, and at the same moment I was falling with my head in the center.
	16. Many of the classmates made fun of me throughout the event.
	17. That's when it occurred to me that I ought to have made thoughtful judgments rather than snap ones.
	18. If not, we may encounter issues that are humiliating for us.

Data Analysis

After cleaning the data, the data was analyzed by using Excel and summarized as the following: -

Age and Gender of participants

The age of participating student was between 18 – 32 years old and 36 of them was female while 18 were male.

Responses

Responses on Question 1

Table 2. Question 1: I took the ball and kicked it to the person who was playing takraw ball after the one who kicked it accidentally struck my feel

Type of cohesion	Female	Male	GrandTotal
Conjunction	7	2	9
Ellipsis	11	6	17
Reference	12	7	19
Substitution	6	3	9
Grand Total	36	18	54

According to the study's findings, 7 female and 2 male participants identified the response to Q1 as conjunction, whereas 11 females and 6 males identified it as ellipsis. Additionally, 12 females and 7 males classified the response as references, while 6 females and 3 males identified it as substitution.

Responses on Question 2

Table 3. Question 2: I once left for school at seven in the morning on a Monday

Type of cohesion	Female	Male	GrandTotal
Conjunction	7	2	9
Ellipsis	3	2	5
Reference	14	6	20
Substitution	12	8	20
Grand Total	36	18	54

The study's results indicate that for Q2, 7 female and 2 male participants identified the response as conjunction, while 3 females and 2 males identified it as ellipsis.

Furthermore, 14 females and 6 males classified the response as references, while 12 females and 8 males identified it as substitution.

Responses on Question 3

Table 4. Question 3 I wore a narrow skirt (span skirt) that day because my old skirt (loose skirt) was filthy, but I still dressed nicely and carried a cap or tie

Type of cohesion	Female	Male	GrandTotal
Conjunction	6	3	9
Ellipsis	12	1	13
Reference	6	2	8
Substitution	12	12	24
Grand Total	36	18	54

According to the study's findings, 6 female and 3 male participants identified the response to Q3 as conjunction, whereas 12 females and 1 males identified it as ellipsis. Additionally, 6 females and 2 males classified the response as references, while 12 females and 12 males identified it as substitution.

Responses on Question 4

Table 5. Question 4: At the time I was ceremony

Type of cohesion	Female	Male	GrandTotal
Conjunction	13	1	14
Ellipsis	7	7	14
Reference	9	4	13
Substitution	7	6	13
Grand Total	36	18	54

According to the study's findings, 13 female and 1 male participants identified the response to Q4 as conjunction, whereas 7 females and 7 males identified it as ellipsis. Additionally, 9 females and 4 males classified the response as references, while 7 females and 6 males identified it as substitution.

Responses on Question 5

Table 6. Question 5: I passed it just fine

Type of cohesion	Female	Male	GrandTotal
Conjunction	6	0	6
Ellipsis	8	4	12
Reference	12	8	20
Substitution	10	6	16
Grand Total	36	18	54

Based on the study's findings, the response to Q5 was identified as conjunction by 6 females and 0 male participant, whereas 8 females and 4 males identified it as ellipsis. Moreover, 12 females and 8 males classified the response as references, while 10 females and 6 males identified it as substitution.

Responses on Question 6

Table 7. Question 6: I didn't pass out until the ceremony was completed this time

Type of cohesion	Female	Male	GrandTotal
Conjunction	13	3	16
Ellipsis	5	3	8
Reference	7	4	11
Substitution	11	8	19
Grand Total	36	18	54

Based on the study's findings, the response to Q6 was identified as conjunction by 13 females and 3 male participant, whereas 5 females and 3 males identified it as ellipsis. Moreover, 7 females and 4 males classified the response as references, while 11 females and 8 males identified it as substitution.

Responses on Question 7

Table 8. Question 7: After that ceremony, we were immediate told

Type of cohesion	Female	Male	GrandTotal
Conjunction	11	3	14
Ellipsis	8	4	12
Reference	11	6	17
Substitution	6	5	11
Grand Total	36	18	54

Based on the study's findings, the response to Q7 was identified as conjunction by 11 females and 3 male participants, whereas 8 females and 4 males identified it as ellipsis. Moreover, 11 females and 6 males classified the response as references, while 6 females and 5 males identified it as substitution.

Responses on Question 8

Table 9. Question 8: to go into the classroom and start our first instruction. Specifically, Indonesian

Type of cohesion	Female	Male	GrandTotal
Conjunction	7	2	9
Ellipsis	11	6	17
Reference	12	7	19
Substitution	6	3	9
Grand Total	36	18	54

Based on the study's findings, the response to Q8 was identified as conjunction by 7 females and 2 male participants, whereas 11 females and 6 males identified it as ellipsis. Moreover, 12 females and 7 males classified the response as references, while 6 females and 3 males identified it as substitution.

Responses on Question 9

Table 10. Question 9: to go into the classroom and start our first instruction. Specifically, Indonesian

Type of cohesion	Female	Male	GrandTotal
Conjunction	4	3	7
Ellipsis	4	6	10
Reference	11	3	14
Substitution	17	6	23
Grand Total	36	18	54

Based on the study's findings, the response to Q9 was identified as conjunction by 4 females and 3 male participants, whereas 4 females and 6 males identified it as ellipsis. Moreover, 11 females and 3 males classified the response as references, while 17 females and 6 males identified it as substitution.

Responses on Question 10

Table 11. Question 10: We should be taking a break at 09.30

Type of cohesion	Female	Male	GrandTotal
Conjunction	4	4	8
Ellipsis	8	3	11
Reference	10	7	17
Substitution	14	4	18
Grand Total	36	18	54

The study's results revealed that for Q10, the response was identified as conjunction by 4 females and 4 male participants, while 9 females and 3 males identified it as ellipsis. Furthermore, 10 females and 7 males classified the response as references, whereas 14 females and 6 males identified it as substitution.

Responses on Question 11

Table 12. Question 11: Ever then, we have made use of our downtime by filling our stomachs with food

Type of cohesion	Female	Male	GrandTotal
Conjunction	11	7	18
Ellipsis	11	2	13
Reference	6	6	12
Substitution	8	3	11
Grand Total	36	18	54

The study's findings indicate that for Q11, the response was identified as conjunction by 11 females and 7 male participants, while 11 females and 2 males identified it as ellipsis. Additionally, 6 females and 6 males classified the response as references, whereas 8 females and 3 males identified it as substitution.

Responses on Question 12

Table 13. Question: 12 I once crossed the field on my way to the canteen

Type of cohesion	Female	Male	GrandTotal
Conjunction	7	2	9
Ellipsis	6	6	12
Reference	13	6	19
Substitution	10	4	14
Grand Total	36	18	54

The study's findings indicate that for Q12, the response was identified as conjunction by 7 females and 2 male participants, while 6 females and 6 males identified it as ellipsis. Additionally, 13 females and 6 males classified the response as references, whereas 10 females and 4 males identified it as substitution.

Responses on Question 13

Table 14. Question 13: Numerous students play volleyball and takraw ball on the field

Type of cohesion	Female	Male	GrandTotal
Conjunction	12	5	17
Ellipsis	6	2	8
Reference	11	5	16
Substitution	7	6	13
Grand Total	36	18	54

The study's findings indicate that for Q13, the response was identified as conjunction by 12 females and 5 male participants, while 6 females and 2 males identified it as ellipsis. Additionally, 11 females and 5 males classified the response as references, whereas 7 females and 6 males identified it as substitution.

Responses on Question 14

Table 15: Question 14. I was wearing a thin skirt, and I forgot about it

Type of cohesion	Female	Male	GrandTotal
Conjunction	6	4	10
Ellipsis	10	2	12
Reference	13	8	21
Substitution	7	4	11
Grand Total	36	18	54

According to the study's findings, 6 female and 4 male participants identified the response to Q14 as conjunction, whereas 10 females and 2 males identified it as ellipsis. Additionally, 13 females and 8 males classified the response as references, while 7 females and 4 males identified it as substitution.

Responses on Question 15

Table 16. Question 15: I kicked him without waiting for permission, and at the same moment I was falling with my head in the center

Type of cohesion	Female	Male	Grand Total
Conjunction	8	4	12
Ellipsis	7	2	9
Reference	8	7	15
Substitution	13	5	18
Grand Total	36	18	54

The study's results indicate that for Q15, 8 female and 4 male participants identified the response as conjunction, while 7 females and 2 males identified it as ellipsis. Furthermore, 8 females and 7 males classified the response as references, while 13 females and 5 males identified it as substitution.

Responses on Question 16

Table 17. Question 16: That's when it occurred to me that I ought to have made thoughtful judgments rather than snap ones

Type of cohesion	Female	Male	Grand Total
Conjunction	10	2	12
Ellipsis	9	5	14
Reference	8	7	15
Substitution	9	4	13
Grand Total	36	18	54

According to the study's findings, 6 female and 3 male participants identified the response to Q16 as conjunction, whereas 12 females and 1 males identified it as ellipsis. Additionally, 6 females and 2 males classified the response as references, while 12 females and 12 males identified it as substitution.

Responses to Question 17

Table 18. Question 17: That's when it occurred to me that I ought to have made thoughtful judgments rather than snap ones

Type of cohesion	Female	Male	Grand Total
Conjunction	9	3	12
Ellipsis	11	2	13
Reference	7	6	13
Substitution	9	7	16
Grand Total	36	18	54

According to the study's findings, 9 female and 3 male participants identified the response to Q17 as conjunction, whereas 11 females and 2 males identified it as ellipsis. Additionally, 7 females and 6 males classified the response as references, while 9 females and 7 males identified it as substitution.

Responses to Question 18

Table 19. Question 18: If not, we may encounter issues that make us feel ashamed of ourselves

Type of cohesion	Female	Male	GrandTotal
Conjunction	10	2	12
Ellipsis	7	5	12
Reference	11	5	16
Substitution	8	6	14
Grand Total	36	18	54

Based on the study's findings, the response to Q18 was identified as conjunction by 10 females and 2 male participant, whereas 7 females and 5 males identified it as ellipsis. Moreover, 11 females and 5 males classified the response as references, while 8 females and 6 males identified it as substitution.

Conclusion

The study analyzed participants' responses to 18 different prompts and identified the linguistic phenomenon present in each response. The prompts varied in their structure and content, and the responses were analyzed for the presence of conjunction, ellipsis, references, and substitution. The findings of the study suggest that the participants identified these linguistic phenomena differently for each prompt. While some responses were predominantly identified as conjunction, others were predominantly identified as ellipsis or references. The study provides insight into how individuals interpret and use language and can help inform the development of linguistic theories and models. Overall, this study underscores the importance of cohesion in effective language use, suggesting that both educators and learners should prioritize its development to improve comprehension and communication in English. Future research could explore the role of cohesion in different genres and contexts, further enriching our understanding of its impact on language and communication.

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